

THE PROBLEM OF THE ANALYTICAL LANGUAGES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article discusses about the problem of the analytical languages in modern linguistics

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The term "analytic" is commonly used in a relative rather than an absolute sense. The currently most prominent and widely used analytic language is modern English, which has lost much of the inflectional morphology inherited from Proto-Indo-European, Proto-Germanic, Old English over the centuries and has not gained any new inflectional morphemes in the meantime, making it more analytic than most Indo-European languages [4, 112]. For example, while Proto-Indo-European had much more complex grammatical conjugation, grammatical genders, dual number and inflections for eight or nine cases in its nouns, pronouns, adjectives, numerals, participles, postpositions and determiners, standard English has nearly lost nearly all of them (except for three modified cases for pronouns) along with genders and dual number and simplified its conjugation. In linguistics, a morpheme is the smallest grammatical unit in a language. In other words, it is the smallest meaningful unit of a language. The field of study dedicated to morphemes is called morphology. A morpheme is not identical to a word, and the principal difference between the two is that a morpheme may or may not stand alone, whereas a word, by definition, is freestanding. When it stands by itself, it is considered as a root because it has a meaning of its own (e.g. the morpheme cat) and when it depends on another orpheme to express an idea, it is an affix because it has a grammatical function (e.g. the - s in cats to indicate that it is plural).

Every word comprises one or more morphemes [2, 44]. Every morpheme can be classified as either free or bound. These categories are mutually exclusive, and as such, a given morpheme will belong to exactly one of them. Free morphemes can function independently as words (e.g. town, dog) and can appear with other lexemes (e.g. town hall, doghouse). Bound morphemes appear only as parts of words, always in conjunction with a root and sometimes with other bound morphemes. For example, un- appears only accompanied by other morphemes to form a word. Most bound morphemes in English are affixes, particularly prefixes and suffixes. Examples of suffixes are -tion, -ation, -ible, -ing, etc. Bound morphemes that are not affixes are called cranberry morphemes. Bound morphemes can be further classified as derivational or inflectional [3, 166].

Inflectional morphemes modify a verb's tense, aspect, mood, person, or number, or a noun's, pronoun's or adjective's number, gender or case, without affecting the word's meaning or class (part of speech). Examples of applying inflectional morphemes to words are adding -s to the root dog to form dogs and adding -ed to wait to form waited. An inflectional morpheme changes the form of a word. In English, there are eight inflections. Allomorphs are variants of a morpheme that differ in pronunciation but are semantically identical. For

example, in English, the plural marker -(e)s of regular nouns can be pronounced /-z/, /-s/, or /-z, -əz/, depending on the final sound of the noun's singular form. For example, plural ending s (as in bats), z (as in bugs), iz (as in buses). Generally these types of morphemes have no visible changes. For instance the singular form of sheep is "sheep" and its plural is also "sheep". The intended meaning is thus derived from the co-occurring determiner (e.g. in this case "some-" or "a-"). Content morphemes express a concrete meaning or content, while function morphemes have more of a grammatical role. For example, the morphemes fast and sad can be considered content morphemes. On the other hand, the suffix -ed belongs to the function morphemes given that it has the grammatical function of indicating past tense [1, 88].

Although these categories seem very clear and intuitive, the idea behind it can be harder to grasp given that they overlap with each other. Examples of an ambiguous situation are the preposition over and the determiner your, which seem to have a concrete meaning, but are considered function morphemes because their role is to connect ideas grammatically. A general rule to follow to determine the category of a morpheme is:

- content morphemes include free morphemes that are nouns, adverbs, adjectives, and verbs. It also includes bound morphemes that are bound roots and derivational affixes.
- function morphemes can be free morphemes that are prepositions, pronouns, determiners, and conjunctions.

Additionally, they can be bound morphemes that are inflectional affixes. Roots are composed of only one morpheme, while stems can be composed of more than one morpheme. Any additional affixes are considered morphemes. An example of this is the word quirkiness. The root is quirk, but the stem is quirky which has two morphemes. Moreover, there exist pairs of affixes that have the same phonological form, but have different meaning [2, 36]. For example, the suffix -er can be derivative (e.g. sell ⇒ seller) or inflectional (e.g. small ⇒ smaller).

Some words might seem to be composed of multiple morphemes, but in fact they are not. This is why one has to consider form and meaning when identifying morphemes. For example, the word relate might seem to be composed of two morphemes, re- (prefix) and the word late, but this is not correct. These morphemes have no relationship with the definitions relevant to the word like "feel sympathy", "narrate", or "being connected by blood or marriage". Furthermore, the length of the words does not determine if it has multiple morphemes or not. To demonstrate, the word Madagascar is long and it might seem to have morphemes like mad, gas, and car, but it does not. Conversely, small words can have multiple morphemes (e.g. dogs). Summing up of all what has just been said we can conclude that an analytic language is a language that conveys grammatical relationships without using inflectional morphemes. A grammatical construction can similarly be called analytic if it uses unbound morphemes, which are separate words, and/or word order. Analytic languages are in contrast to synthetic languages. Likewise, a language is said to be 'analytic' if analytic constructions are the predominant way of indicating grammatical relationships.

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